

A parametric study on strawberry radiated shaped monopole antenna for ultrawide-band applications

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ABSTRACT

This article gives a parametric study on strawberry-shaped monopole antennas for ultra-wideband (UWB) systems. The antenna design consisted of three different parametric design steps to structure the strawberry radiated monopole antenna. The scheduled strawberry monopole antenna was simulated on an FR4 substrate in a low profile for UWB applications. The total physical dimension is 26 mm×26 mm×1.6 mm, corresponding to the centre frequency of 7.5 GHz. The strawberry antenna is fed via a coplanar waveguide (CPW) to attain the best impedance matching for UWB systems. The presented monopole antenna has an impedance UWB bandwidth of 11.0 GHz from 2.6 GHz up to 13.6 GHz at -10 dB return loss. The simulated UWB strawberry monopole antenna displays an omnidirectional radiation behaviour with a simulated gain of 7.3 dB at 13.6 GHz, a directivity of 7.5 dBi at 13.6 GHz and favourable radiation efficiency of 97%. The proposed monopole UWB strawberry antenna has the technological possibility to be used for UWB applications.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Ultra-wideband (UWB) technology was first approved by the federal communication commission (US-FCC) in 2002, and it has advanced at a fantastic rate in the last few years [1], [2]. The US-FCC has assigned the frequency band 3.1-10.6 GHz for commercial use of the UWB [3]. Many new telecommunication applications and techniques appear daily to achieve UWB response [4], [5]. The main aim of UWB technology is to transmit or receive data with more effective data rates over short-range wireless communication systems using the current communication standards [6], [7]. It is also used in military applications due to its low probability of being intercepted by undesired receivers, which makes it more secure than other communication techniques [8], [9]. The primary complications UWB technology faces are interfering with other narrow band technologies functioning in a frequency band working by the UWB band [10], [11]. Some the examples of these narrow bands are the wireless local area network (WLAN) (IEEE802) and HIPERLAN/2 WLAN operating in the 5-6 GHz band [12]–[15]. In addition to these technologies comes the worldwide interoperation for microwave access (WiMAX) service working in the 3.3-3.6 GHz band [16].

Using filters is not a practical solution due to filters complexity of filters, so the proposed antenna will be integrated with the notched filter [17], [18].

Several antenna techniques and patch shapes have been suggested and presented in recent years to obtain UWB response over wide ranges of frequencies. In [19]–[22], a super compact antenna was proposed to achieve a wide range of frequencies. An ellipsoidal was offered in [23] to obtain a UWB operation from 3.29-9.35 GHz, with a total size of $27 \times 36 \times 1.6$ mm. On the other hand, a leaf-shaped [24] and a broken heart [25] were also presented to attain a wide impedance bandwidth. In addition, a few methods have also been investigated lately to get UWB working bandwidth response [26]–[30].

This study proposes a deep parametric study to verify the strawberry patch antenna. Three progressive stages were introduced in terms of antenna performance, such as reflection coefficient (S11), gain, directivity, efficiency and radiation patterns. All the simulations are performed employing computer simulation technology (CST) Microwave studio 2016.

2. METHOD

2.1. Parametric evolution of the UWB strawberry antenna

The suggested antenna design consists of a circular slot carved into an ionic plane burned on the FR4 laminate of a dielectric constant of 4.3 and a loss tangent of 0.02, with dimensions $(26 \text{ mm} \times 26 \text{ mm} \times 1.6 \text{ mm})$. Two rectangular semi-discs with 50Ω coplanar waveguide (CPW) tapered tubes were established to feed the circular slot to complete the sub-objective. Moreover, a comprehensive parametric study was conducted to validate the UWB design process. Presenting three progressive stages depending on the plant's genetic makeup of the monopole antenna's strawberry fruits are shown in Figure 1. The outcomes of these stages are presented next.

The basic disc globose-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (globose design antenna A), globose-conic shaped monopole antenna with CPW-fed (globose-conic design antenna B), strawberry-shaped monopole antenna with CPW-fed (strawberry design antenna C) and all these three stages of antennas were planned and simulated utilising CST. Afterwards, the investigation done, and the final antenna design (design C) has been carefully chosen and fabricated in the fabrication laboratory. The five different development stages for the UWB monopole antenna (design antenna A to design antenna C) are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Morphology characteristics of some strawberry leaves

Figure 2. The design development stage of the UWB strawberry crop guide monopole antenna (design antenna A to design antenna C)

In addition, some relevant results have been considered to make sure the performance of the monopole antenna is suitable for UWB applications. These results are shown in terms of return loss (dB),

A parametric study on strawberry radiated shaped monopole antenna ... (Ahmed Jamal Abdullah Al-Gburi)

antenna gain (dB), directivity (dB), radiation pattern, and efficiency (%), including the e-field and h-field of the suggested antenna. The good condition of return loss performance must be less than -10 dB to cater to at least 90% of the signal for transmitting and receiving activity.

2.2. Globose-shaped monopole antenna with coplanar waveguide fed (design antenna A)

The first stage in this study consists of a primary circular monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna A). The basic antenna dimensions are 26×26 mm with a copper thickness of 0.02 mm, while the FR-4 substrate thickness is 1.6 mm. When the radius (r) equals 5.4 mm, the disc's diameter is equal to 10.8 mm, as presented in Figures 3(a) and (b), which means by the one-sixth wavelength at the first resonant frequency about 19.0 mm.

Figure 3. Globose-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna A); (a) front view and (b) back look

The feed line length is 6.8 mm and 3.65 mm of his width, connecting with the SMA connector. Moreover, the loss tangent of the FR4 laminate is 0.02 . Figure 4 shows the return loss of the globose-shaped monopole antenna's performance with CPW fed (design antenna B). From Figure 4, it can be observed that the antenna bandwidth is wide, and it operates between 3.6 GHz and 8.5 GHz of frequencies with 4.87 GHz bandwidth performance. It also radiates at 4.66 GHz of WLAN frequency point with a return loss performance of -28.76 dB, while it has a resonant frequency at 6.37 GHz with -29.6 dB.

Figure 4. Return loss performance of the globose-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna A)

2.3. Globose-conic shaped monopole antenna with coplanar waveguide fed (design antenna B)

Next, the second stage consists of designing a globose-conic-shaped monopole antenna with CPW-fed (design antenna B), as presented in Figures 5(a) and (b). At this stage, there are three-circular radius has

been added to shape the globose-conic radiated patch. These circular patches are r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 . The r_1 value is about 5.4mm. A triangle is created from the intersection between three circles to measure each circle's total area. These triangles are (a, b, c); the famous formulas are used to calculate the total area of a circle and triangle, respectively. Where $A=\pi r^2$, $A=(hb \times b)/2$, A referred is the entire area, and r is the radius. Whereas hb is the height of the triangle, and b is the triangle base. The globose-conic radiated patch technique is used to improve the bandwidth of the UWB frequencies. Moreover, once r equals 5.4 mm, the diameter of the conic ($2 \times (r_1/2 + r_2/2 + r_3/2)$) is 16.2 mm.

Figure 5. The design geometry of globose-conic shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna B); (a) front view and (b) back look

Figure 6 presents the return loss performance of the globose-conic shaped antenna with CPW fed (design antenna B). The results from Figure 6 indicated that the antenna is radiated at a wide range of frequencies with a bandwidth of 4.6 GHz (3.03 -7.63 GHz), and it also emits at a resonant frequency of 3.86 GHz with -28.51 dB. Furthermore, the return loss performance at 5.2 GHz is -23.37 dB.

Figure 6. Return loss performance of the globose-conic shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna B)

2.4. Strawberry-shaped-monopole antenna with modified coplanar waveguide fed (design antenna C)

The suggested planar antenna was simulated by employing CST-studio software. The proposed antenna structure consists of a circular slot etched into a metallic plane printed on the FR4 substrate of a dielectric constant of 4.3 and a loss tangent of 0.02, with dimensions (26 mm ×26 mm×1.6 mm). To accomplish the first sub-objective, a CPW feed with 50Ω CPW tapered lines were placed to feed the proposed antenna.

Figures 7(a) and (b) characterise the design of the UWB planar antenna with CPW fed. The total size of the modelled antenna is 26 mm $\times$ 26 mm $\times$ 1.6 mm. The planar radiated patch is made from a seven circular discs to structure the modelled antenna. In this stage, the CPW fed was cut off from the inner side and denoted as Clc , as illustrated in Figure 7. The bandwidth expands due to the available space between the feed line and the CPW, which allows the creation of the certified UWB from 2.6 up to 13.7 GHz; besides that, it enhances the impedance matching between the feed and the emitted patch. Table 1 records all the antenna specifications.

Figure 7. The design geometry of the UWB strawberry antenna; (a) front look and (b) back look

Table 1. The proportions of the UWB strawberry antenna (design antenna C)

Antennas description	Variables	Sizes (mm)
Substrate width	W	26
Substrate length	L	26
The four cylinders radius	$r1, r2, r3, r4, r5, r6$	5.4
The spacing between cylinder radius	S	3.8
Feed-line width	Wf	3.65
Feed-line length	Lf	6.8
CPW width	Cw	11.15
CPW length	Cl	7.5
CPW adjusted length	Cwc	8.7
The gap between CPW and the fed line	g	0.525
CPW adjusted height	Clc	1.6
Thickness of copper	Tc	0.02
Thickness of substrate	Ts	1.6

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this stage, the simulated outcomes of the CPW-fed UWB strawberry antenna have been validated to determine the best characteristics design of the simulated strawberry-shaped monopole antenna. Figures 8(a) to (d) present the simulated reflection coefficient, gain, directivity and efficiency of the proposed UWB strawberry antenna. The simulated antenna obtained a bandwidth of 11.1 GHz from 2.6 GHz to 13.6 GHz. It resonates at three main frequencies as follows: i) 3.35 GHz with -19.24 dB of return loss performance for simulation; ii) resonant frequency at 8.16 GHz with -32.12 dB of return loss performance for simulation, and iii) third resonant frequency at 10.7 GHz with return loss performance of -50 dB. The proposed antenna achieved a gain value of 7.3 dB at 13.6 GHz and high directivity of 7.5 dBi at the same frequency, which is 13.6 GHz. The UWB strawberry antenna obtains a high radiation efficiency of 97%.

Figures 9(a) and (b) show the radiation pattern of the strawberry-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna C) at 2.911 GHz and 7.74 GHz. It presents that the radiation pattern at 2.911 GHz for H-field looks like omnidirectional while the e-field looks pear-shaped. Moreover, the radiation pattern looks different at 7.74 GHz. Meanwhile, for the h-field, it seems kidney-shaped, with a minor lobe at the bottom part.

Figure 8. Simulated results of (a) reflection coefficient (S11), (b) gain, (c) directivity and (d) radiation efficiency

Figure 9. H-field and e-field radiation patterns of the strawberry-shaped monopole antenna with CPW fed (design antenna C) at (a) 2.911 GHz and (b) 7.74 GHz

4. CONCLUSION

A deep parametric study to verify the strawberry patch antenna is proposed in this paper. Three advanced stages were introduced to structure the strawberry antenna (design A to design D), in terms of antenna performance, such as reflection coefficient (S11), gain, directivity, efficiency and radiation patterns. The proposed strawberry UWB antenna achieved a good performance. For example, a gain of 7.3 dB was received at 13.6 GHz, with a high directivity of 7.5 dBi. The simulated UWB antenna achieved an excellent efficiency of 97%, with a Fractional bandwidth of 93%, making the proposed UWB strawberry antenna suitable to be operated for UWB systems.

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REFERENCES

[1] Federal Communications Commission, "Revision of part 15 of the commission's rules regarding ultra-wideband transmission systems," 2002. [Online]. Available: <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/naid/10011635689/>

- [2] D. Dardari, A. Conti, U. Ferner, A. Giorgetti, and M. Z. Win, "Ranging with ultrawide bandwidth signals in multipath environments," in *Proceedings of the IEEE*, Feb. 2009, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 404–426. doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2008.2008846.
- [3] W. S. Yeoh and W. S. T. Rowe, "An UWB conical monopole antenna for multiservice wireless applications," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 14, pp. 1085–1088, 2015, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2015.2394295.
- [4] R. V. S. R. Krishna and R. Kumar, "A dual-polarized square-ring slot antenna for UWB, imaging, and radar applications," *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 15, pp. 195–198, 2016, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2015.2438013.
- [5] S. Kim, Y. Kim, X. Li, and J. Kang, "Orthogonal pulse design in consideration of FCC and IEEE 802.15.4a constraints," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 896–899, May 2013, doi: 10.1109/LCOMM.2013.040213.122936.
- [6] A. Domazetovic, L. J. Greenstein, N. B. Mandayam, and I. Seskar, "Propagation models for short-range wireless channels with predictable path geometries," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 1123–1126, Jul. 2005, doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2005.851606.
- [7] C. Marchais, G. L. Ray, and A. Sharaiha, "UWB antennas time domain characterization," in *11th International Symposium on Antenna Technology and Applied Electromagnetics [ANTEM 2005]*, Jun. 2005, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/ANTEM.2005.7852122.
- [8] L. Barbieri, M. Brambilla, R. Pitic, A. Trabattoni, S. Mervic, and M. Nicoli, "UWB real-time location systems for smart factory: Augmentation methods and experiments," in *2020 IEEE 31st Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*, Aug. 2020, pp. 1–7. doi: 10.1109/PIMRC48278.2020.9217307.
- [9] A. D. K. Al-Obaidi, O. Ghazali, M. Mahmuddin, A. J. A. Al-Gburi, M. N. M. Al-Niamey, and M. F. Mansor, "High efficiency dielectric resonator antenna using complementary ring resonator for bandwidth enhancement," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 2107–2114, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i4.3681.
- [10] A. J. A. Al-Gburi, I. Ibrahim, Z. Zakaria, and A. D. Khaleel, "Bandwidth and gain enhancement of ultra-wideband monopole antenna using MEBG structure," *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 3390–3393, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.36478/jeasci.2019.3390.3393.
- [11] M. Y. Zeain *et al.*, "Design of a wideband strip helical antenna for 5G applications," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 1958–1963, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i5.2055.
- [12] R. A. A. Kamaruddin *et al.*, "Return loss improvement of radial line slot array antennas on closed ring resonator structure at 28 GHz," *PRZEGLĄD ELEKTROTECHNICZNY*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 67–71, May 2021, doi: 10.15199/48.2021.05.10.
- [13] A. A. Jabber and R. H. Thaher, "Compact tri-band T-shaped frequency reconfigurable antenna for cognitive radio applications," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 212–220, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.11591/eei.v9i1.1708.
- [14] M. M. J. Abed *et al.*, "Design and characterization substrate integrated waveguide antenna for WBANS application," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 1390–1398, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i3.3492.
- [15] A. J. A. Al-Gburi, I. M. Ibrahim, and Z. Zakaria, "An ultra-miniaturized MCPM antenna for ultra-wideband applications," *Journal of Nano- and Electronic Physics*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1–4, 2021, doi: 10.21272/jnep.13(5).05012.
- [16] A. H. Majeed and K. H. Sayidmarie, "UWB elliptical patch monopole antenna with dual-band notched characteristics," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3591–3598, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i5.pp3591-3598.
- [17] A. Q. Kamil and A. K. Jassim, "Design ultra-wideband antenna have a band rejection desired to avoid interference from existing bands," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 886–892, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i2.3164.
- [18] A. Abbas *et al.*, "A rectangular notch-band UWB antenna with controllable notched bandwidth and centre frequency," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1–11, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20030777.
- [19] A. J. A. Al-Gburi *et al.*, "Super compact uwb monopole antenna for small iot devices," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 73, no. 2, pp. 2785–2799, 2022, doi: 10.32604/cmcc.2022.028074.
- [20] P. Mayuri, N. D. Rani, N. B. Subrahmanyam, and B. T. P. Madhav, "Design and analysis of a compact reconfigurable dual band notched UWB antenna," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 98, pp. 141–153, 2020, doi: 10.2528/PIERC19082903.
- [21] M. O. Al-Dwairi, "A planar UWB semicircular-shaped monopole antenna with quadruple band notch for WiMAX, ARN, WLAN, and X-Band," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 908–918, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i1.pp908-918.
- [22] A. A. Jabber, A. K. Jassim, and R. H. Thaher, "Compact reconfigurable PIFA antenna for wireless applications," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 595–602, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.12928/telkomnika.v18i2.13427.
- [23] H. S. Mewara, D. Jhanwar, M. M. Sharma, and J. K. Deegwal, "A printed monopole ellipsoidal UWB antenna with four band rejection characteristics," *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, vol. 83, pp. 222–232, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.aeue.2017.08.043.
- [24] A. Iqbal, O. A. Saraereh, and S. K. Jaiswal, "Maple leaf shaped UWB monopole antenna with dual band notch functionality," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 71, pp. 169–175, 2017, doi: 10.2528/PIERC17010801.
- [25] N. Rahman, M. T. Islam, Z. Mahmud, and M. Samsuzzaman, "The broken-heart printed antenna for ultrawideband applications: Design and characteristics analysis," *IEEE Antennas and Propagation Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 45–51, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/MAP.2018.2870664.
- [26] A. H. Majeed, K. H. Sayidmarie, F. M. A. Abdussalam, R. A. Abd-Alhameed, and A. Alhaddad, "A microstrip-fed pentagon patch monopole antenna for ultra wideband applications," in *2015 Internet Technologies and Applications (ITA)*, Sep. 2015, pp. 452–456. doi: 10.1109/ITechA.2015.7317446.
- [27] A. J. A. Al-Gburi, I. B. M. Ibrahim, Z. Zakaria, and N. F. B. M. Nazli, "Wideband microstrip patch antenna for sub 6 GHz and 5G applications," *Przeegląd Elektrotechniczny*, vol. 97, no. 11, pp. 26–29, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.15199/48.2021.11.04.
- [28] S. Ullah, C. Ruan, M. S. Sadiq, T. U. Haq, and W. He, "High efficient and ultra wide band monopole antenna for microwave imaging and communication applications," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3390/s20010115.
- [29] H. Alwareth, I. M. Ibrahim, Z. Zakaria, A. J. A. Al-Gburi, S. Ahmed, and Z. A. Nasser, "A wideband high-gain microstrip array antenna integrated with frequency-selective surface for Sub-6 GHz 5G applications," *Micromachines*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 1–19, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/mi13081215.
- [30] K. H. Sayidmarie and Y. A. Fadhel, "UWB fractal monopoles of rectangular and triangular shapes," in *2011 4th IEEE International Symposium on Microwave, Antenna, Propagation and EMC Technologies for Wireless Communications*, Nov. 2011, pp. 709–712. doi: 10.1109/MAPE.2011.6156214.

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